

DEVELOPING CULTURAL READING LEARNING MATERIALS OF LITERATURE FOR JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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Abstract

Culture is embodied by the language. Studying language is studying the culture itself. It means that culture cannot be separated with the target language. In learning English, literature is believed to have much influence on the English language. This is because literature can keep the students' sensitivity to the use of English. This study presents the Research and Development (R&D) type. The research allowed some stages. The stages were conducting needs analysis, planning, designing the materials, experts judgements, revising, evaluating or trying the materials, and writing the final draft of the materials. The research involves 30 participants in a Junior High School of Wonosari, Gunungkidul. The data of this research were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The data from the research findings show that the appropriate English learning materials for the students consist of three units. The materials was then developed from the three most preferable themes, the love, virtue, and honesty. Then, there were three literary works for each theme namely poetry, story, and play. From the results of the materials evaluation, the mean values (\bar{x}) of the statements were 3.78 to 4.50. Those ranges were categorized as good and very good. The data were supported by the interview, and observation. It can be concluded that cultural reading learning materials of literature were appropriate for the junior high school students in Wonosari, Gunungkidul.

Keywords: cultural, reading learning materials, literature.

Introduction

English has become an international language used by people in the world. People use this international language to share global information and to communicate in this globalization era. In relation with the used of English globally, many countries have prepared the society in facing the globalization by positioning English as part of education.

Nowadays in EFL context, English subject is taught as one of the important subjects in junior high school. English is taught not only to develop the students' intelligence and knowledge of English but also communicative English that should include cross-cultural understanding. Fries and Lado (2007: 149) states that to deal with the culture and life of the people of the

language being learned is not just an adjunct of a practical language course but also an essential feature of every stage of language learning. It means that literature is believed to be essential in helping the students to learn.

In addition, Shanahan (2007: 168) states that cultural content provides exposure to living language that a foreign language student lacks. In this case, culture is embodied by the language. Studying language is studying the culture itself. It means that culture cannot be separated with the target language. In learning English, literature is believed to have much influence on the English language. This is because literature can keep the students' sensitivity to the use of English.

However, the existence of cultural reading learning materials of literature for junior high school students are still limited. Many course books are less of English cultural context. This condition caused the students to be text-books rather than communicative. Many of the students speak English like but actually it still Indonesian. This case happened because cultures are separated with the language use in many course books.

It means that Literature materials are important to help the students in learning English communicatively. It also needed to facilitate the students in achieving good English competence. Therefore, developing cultural reading learning materials of literature for junior high school students becomes an important thing to the teachers.

Literature Review

a. English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

Hutchinson and Waters (1987: 19) defines ESP as an approach rather than a product. In this case, need is defined by considering the reasons of the students in learning English. In short, ESP is an approach to language teaching in which all decisions to the contents and methods are based on the students' reasons to learn.

Similarly, Munby in Kim (2008: 11) states that "ESP courses are designed based on the prior analysis of communicative needs of the learners compared to the predetermined nature of general English syllabi". Since ESP courses are designed by considering students' needs,

students become the center in making the course design. This course design will be used to make the materials that are appropriate to them.

In addition, Dudley-Evans and St John (1998: 19) in Miguel (2010: 1) says that “ESP is essentially materials and teaching led movement.” It is closely interlinked with Applied Linguistics and English Language Teaching. They also point out that ESP is different from other academic disciplines. The professions, the genres, and registers are different with common English in general. Then, Nunan (2004:7) says that English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has its own approaches on curriculum development, and materials design development.

It can be concluded that the materials in ESP program are specific and different from those in general English because they are based on students’ reasons in learning. In designing the materials, course design that is appropriate with the students’ needs will also be considered. Their English learning is closely related to the English in their workfield which has its own approach.

b. Culture

Brown (2001: 46) defines culture as the ideas, customs, skills, arts, and tools that characterize a group of people in a period of time. In addition, Jiang (2000: 92) states that culture and language are not separated. It means that culture is embedded with the target language. Studying language and the culture is believed to have many beneficial in English language learning sensitivity.

c. Reading

In the previous section, Grabe (2009:5) defines reading as the process in which readers learn something from what they read and involve it in academic context as a part of education. It is believed as an important skill to support the students in understanding and decoding the learning materials. Furthermore, reading is also important in social context where the activity of reading takes place. It makes people around the world will be able to communicate with the other.

According to Harmer (2001:200), reading is important for getting information. The reason why reading is important can be divided into two categories, instrumental and pleasurable aspects. The instrumental aspect will help the reader to achieve some clear aim and it covers getting information from the written source and understanding the instruction what the readers need to do.

Meanwhile, the pleasurable aspect deals with the reading for pleasure. It can be in the form of reading the magazine or interpreting the illustration of a picture. However, the main point of its essence is that learners will get some information from the reading activity and gradually they will be able to communicate with the others.

d. Literature

In a widest sense, literature is just about anything written (Kennedy, 1979). It means that any kinds of written texts such as newspaper, article, gossips, Mathematics, History, Biology books, leaflet, food labels, recipe and ticket can be called as literature. In addition, Harry Shaw (1997: 201) states that literature is writing products which expression and form, in connection with ideas and concerns of universal and permanent interest, are its essential features. From this definition, it can be conclude that not all of writings are literature. Furthermore, Tjahjono(2007: 34) mentions that literary language has some characteristics that are different with scientific writing. Literary language is connotative, multi-interpretable and has musicality effect. It means that literature is writing products which are different with scientific writing such as fiction story, poem, drama, etc.

e. Materials

According to Tomlinson (1998: 2), materials are anything which is used by the teachers or learners to facilitate the learning. It means that material is the essential part in teaching learning process. It can facilitate the learning of language. Materials, in fact, provide concrete models in classroom practice, act as curriculum models, and fulfill the teacher development role. Therefore, the kind of materials will influence the learning of language.

Material is anything which can be used to help language teaching. Materials can be in the form of textbooks, workbooks, cassettes, videos, handouts, etc. In short, materials can be

anything which are free used in developing the students' knowledge and experience of the language (Tomlinson, 1998: 2). This is important to know that the materials are good or not. Tomlinson (1998: 7-21) identifies criteria of good materials as follows.

Materials should achieve impact, materials should help learners to feel at ease, materials should expose the learners to language in authentic use, materials should provide the learners with opportunities to use the target language to achieve communicative purposes, materials should not rely too much on controlled practice. In conclusion, materials that are attractive, encouraging students' motivation, authentic, providing opportunity to be communicative learners, and varied from guided into free guided will be good to be designed for teaching and learning process.

Research Methods

The research design is research and Development since its purpose was to develop a finished product that can be used appropriately in an educational program (Borg, 2003:772).

Research Subjects

The research subject are 30 Students of Grade VIII at SMP Muhammadiyah 2 Wonosari.

Data Collection Techniques

The data collection techniques used some questionnaires. Firstly, the data of the target and learning needs in English were collected at the early stage of the research through the needs analysis questionnaires. Secondly, opinion and suggestion from the experts to find the appropriateness of the designed materials before the tryouts were reached through the expert judgements questionnaire. The instruments used to collect the data in this research were questionnaires and interview guides. This research used two approaches of collecting information. Those are quantitative and qualitative.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed differently.

a. Data from Questionnaires

There were three kinds of questionnaires, the researcher analyzed the data differently. For the needs analysis, the researcher used percentages. For the experts judgement questionnaires, the researcher used frequencies. Then, for the materials try-out questionnaire, the researcher used frequencies and descriptive statistics.

Then, to put all the mean values in the categories, range was used to classify the mean values in classes (Suharto, 2006: 52). The method for calculating the mean was the same as that in the score conversion, i.e. finding the class interval for determining the category. The class interval was calculated based on the following procedure: firstly, we has had to find the formula ($R = X_{\text{highest}} - X_{\text{lowest}}$), then the result of the calculation was divided by the desired number of the class (in this case 5 classes). Based on the calculation, the class intervals were presented as follows:

Table 1: Quantitative Data Conversion (Suharto, 2006: 52)

Scales	Categories	Interval of Mean
5	very good	4.20-5.00
4	Good	3.40-4.19
3	Fair	2.60-3.39
2	Poor	1.80-2.59
1	very poor	1.00-1.79

Data from Interviews

The qualitative data obtained from the interviews were recorded and then transcribed. The data in the form of interview transcripts were analyzed based on the qualitative data analysis from Miles and Huberman (1994: 120). The qualitative data were analyzed in four steps. The first step was collecting the data. The second step was data reduction. In this step, the researcher selected limited, simplified, and transformed the data by summarizing or paraphrasing the interview transcripts. The next step was data display. The last step was drawing the conclusions.

Research Procedures

This research used Research and Development proposed by Borg and Gall. As a basis of developing the materials, the researcher used the system approach model from Dick & Carey in Borg and Gall (2003: 571). The procedure of the research will be described below:

1) Step 1: Needs analysis

The needs analysis was done to gather the information of the learning and the learners' needs. Then, the data were analyzed as the basis of developing English learning materials for the learners.

2) Step 2: Planning

In this stage, the course grid was developed based on the students' needs. The course grid consisted of topic, unit title, language function, input text, language focus that covers key vocabulary and key grammar, learning procedure/ activities, and achievement indicators.

3) Step 3: Developing the materials

The English materials were developed based on the course grid.

4) Step 4: Expert Judgements

The materials were consulted to the first consultant and the second consultant as well as the experts to gain feedback.

5) Step 5: Revising

The feedbacks from the experts were used for writing the second draft.

6) Step 6: Evaluating the materials

The materials were then tried out. It involved 30 students at SMP in Wonosari. At the end of the try-out, the second questionnaires were distributed to know the students' comments on the appropriateness of the materials. The students were interviewed to reach detailed feedback on the appropriateness of the materials. This feedback was used for evaluating the materials.

7) Step 7: Writing the final draft

The results of the questionnaire and the interviews were analyzed and used to evaluate and revise materials in order to get the final material. The final result of this research was a set of English learning materials for SMP in Wonosari students.

Discussions

a. The result of the needs analysis

1) Data from the questionnaire

Students' attitude toward English and students' reading habit are positive. More than 78% students gave positive answers to the questions concerning their attitude toward English and 72, 75% students gave positive answer answers to the questions concerning the reading habit

The students have poor experience on English literature, because more than 45, 42% students stated that they had never read English literary works and few who had read stated that they could not understand it.

The approach of using literature in the language classroom that is most preferable by the students is using literature. It can be seen from 89, 38% positive answer from the students.

The preferable themes in literature that had been chosen by the students are the virtue 87, 5%, love 86, 25%, and honesty 82,50%.

2) Data from the interview

Data from the interview shows that the study of literature should not go very deep. It should be suitable with the students English mastery level. Therefore simplified text was suggested because by using simplified text the difficulty that is caused by insufficient vocabulary mastery could be reduced.

b. Instructional design

The preliminary data describe above was then used as one consideration in designing instructional materials in which approach, objectives and basis of materials selection should be determined.

From the questionnaire, it could be seen that students prefer to discuss themes of literary works and compare them with their own experience .

The objectives of teaching English literature at one of the SMP in Wonosari, Gunungkidul is to introduce English literature to the students as a means to develop students' language skills.

The selection of the materials is based on the result of the interview and questionnaire. There are three themes included and this materials namely love, virtue, and honesty.

The materials design is thematic type. It means that the topic interest and areas of subject knowledge selected as themes to be read or talked about order to learn the language.

For each theme, three kinds of literary works namely short story, poetry, and extracts of play are included.

The materials is arranged following Collie's arrangement in which for each kind of literary work, there are three kinds of actvtis namely pre-reading, while-reading, andpost-reading.

c. Unit Design

In this part three units of materials were developed. Each unit contains the following elements.

THEME

A. Poetry

1. Pre-reading activity (starter)
2. While reading activity (input)
3. Post-reading activity (language and content)

B. Short Story

- 1) Pre-reading activity (starter)
- 2) While reading activity (input)
- 3) Post-reading activity (language and content)

C. Play

1. Pre-reading activity (starter)
2. While reading activity (input)
3. Post-reading activity (language and content)

d. Activity design

Learning activities are determined based on the objectives of the teaching of English by using literature, that is, to introduce English literature as a means to develop the student's reading skills.

Those activities are described as follows:

1) Pre-reading activities

Stimulating students' interest in the text

- Predicting the theme of the text from its title
- Discussing or describing pictures relevant to the text
- Discussing "what they would do and how they would respond" if they were in the similar situation to the one in the poem.

Providing the necessary historical and political background

- Reading or listening to a text which describe the historical and political background of the text
- Reading to a text about author's life
- Discussing what are the appropriate behaviors or feelings in their culture in the particular situation and comparing with those in the text.

Helping the students with the language

- Pre teaching any important words, phrases or grammatical construction that appear in the text.

2) While-reading activities

Poem

- Jumbling up verses
- Filling the gap caused by the removal words
- Predicting what is coming next
- Underlying the words with a particular lexical set and speculating their meaning
- Answering comprehension questions about the meaning of certain words.

Short Story

Helping the students to understand the plot

- Writing a brief summary of the plot
- Making a title for each paragraph
- Jumbling up sentences which summarize the plot
- Sentence completion exercise

Helping the students to understand the character

- Choosing from a list of adjectives which is most appropriate for describing a particular character
- Ranking the character of the story according to certain traits

Helping the students with difficult vocabulary

- Providing definitions for certain word in the text
- Providing multiple choice questions to encourage the guessing of meaning from context

3) Post reading activities

- Providing the students with different interpretation of the text

- Writing a review of the text
- Reading aloud (poem) and decide what mime or what gesture is appropriate
- Role play or acting out scene from the text
- Discussing the universal value despite in the text.

e. Revision

From the questionnaire and interview on the materials that have been tried out. These are some revision on the materials.

- 1) Definition of some words which are unfamiliar to the students but appear in the text frequently are given as footnotes
- 2) The questions of each sub-title of the short stories are not given at the end of the story but at the end of each sub-title to help the students to understand the texts which are considered too long
- 3) Before reading the text a situation is given to arouse the students' interest in the universal value of the story.

f. Model of the Materials.

Three units of learning materials of literature were develop. The three units had been tried out to the students at the SMP in Wonosari and revised. Here are some parts of the final models that will be presented as follows.

UNIT I	UNIT II	UNIT III
LOVE	VIRTUE	HONESTY
I The Poem	I The Poem	I The Poem
Task 1	Task 1	Task 1
Task 2	Task 2	Task 2
Task 3	Task 3	Task 3
II The Story	II The Story	II The Story
Task 4	Task 4	Task 4
Task 5	Task 5	Task 5
Task 6	Task 6	Task 6
III The Play	III The Play	III The Play
Task 7	Task 7	Task 7
Task 8	Task 8	Task 8
Task 9	Task 9	Task 9

UNIT 1 LOVE

I The Poem

Task 1. In pairs, complete the following sentences.

Fountains always mingle with...

The rivers always mingle with...

The mountain peaks touch...

The sun always lights...

II The Story

Task 4. Read the text attentively.

The Nightingale dies

The she gave one last song. So wonderful was the music that the moon heard it and the moon forgot the sunrise and stayed in the sky. The red rose also heard it and opened the leaves to the cold morning air.

"Look, look!" cried the tree, "the rose is finished now". But The Nightingale made no answer. She was dead with the thorn in her heart.

III The Play

Task 7. Read and Practice.

A Doll's House

Nora. Just now. (*Puts the bag of macaroons into her pocket and wipes her mouth.*) Come in here, Torvald, and see what I have bought.

Helmer. Don't disturb me. (*A little later, he opens the door and looks into the room, pen in hand.*) Bought, did you say? All these things? Has my little spendthrift been wasting money again?

Nora. Yes, but, Torvald, this year we really can let ourselves go a little. This is the first Christmas that we have not needed to economize.

Helmer. Still, you know, we can't spend money recklessly.

Nora. Yes, Torvald, we may be a wee bit more reckless now, mayn't we? Just a tiny wee bit! You are going to have a big salary and earn lots and lots of money.

Helmer. Yes, after the New Year; but then it will be a whole quarter before the salary is due.

Nora. Pooh! we can borrow till then.

Conclusion

From the needs assessment, it was found out that the most interesting themes for them are virtue, love, and honesty. The approach of the teaching of literature considered to be most suitable and advantageous is the using of literary text in English classrooms as a mean of personal enrichment. The objectives formulated after the needs analysis is to introduce English literature as a means to develop students' reading skills.

The next steps is selecting and organizing the materials. The first draft of the materials then consulted to the experts. Then the revised draft from the experts then tried out to the students. Based on the students' feedback, the final drafts of the materials are produced. The final materials was then developed from the three most preferable themes, the virtue, love, and honesty. Then, there were three literary works for each theme namely poetry, story, and play.

From the results of the materials evaluation, the mean values (\bar{x}) of the statements were 3.78 to 4.50. Those ranges were categorized as good and very good. The data were supported by the interview, and observation. It can be concluded that cultural reading learning materials of literature were appropriate for the junior high school students in Wonosari, Gunungkidul.

Suggestion

From the observation of the students' responses to the literature teaching, the students were very enthusiastic in dealing with and discussing about themes taken from the literary works that resemble their own life experience. The result of their test on the subject also showed that literary works were not impossible to be learned and comprehend by them.

Referring to that, the writer thinks that it is about time for curriculum developers to start including literature as parts of English classroom teaching because it provides the real English culture that also close to the students' life. This kind of teaching will also powerful to help them to learn the language and keep the students' sensitivity to the use of English.

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